

S3 Table. Representative answers obtained from participants at the end of the IV Python for Biological Data Workshop, held in 2021.

Question	Category	Answer
How would you improve this course?	Making the notebooks available	"I think making the notebooks available at the end of the course could be interesting for those who are learning and missed some parts."
		"Providing the notebooks with the practical activity codes ready, and commenting on the codes during the class. This would help students focus on the explanation and prevent constant interruptions due to difficulties in typing the codes and following the explanation simultaneously."
		"I would like to suggest providing an outline of the topics that will be covered each day. If the class recording and the notebook are not made available, perhaps a practice outline for the student to follow later could help."
	Workload	"I believe the schedule could be better distributed. I found it heavy to have just one day dedicated to group and individual activities."
		"Better organizing the day for individual and group exercises. Having both due on the same day was detrimental to the performance of at least one of them."
		"Having more time for the exercises (extended deadlines) felt tight."
What was your experience participating in the distance learning course? Would you take another course in the same format?	Positive experience	"I enjoyed the experience in the distance learning course. I don't see myself being able to travel to the event location if it were in another format. I would definitely attend another event in this format."
		"I found the experience very good. The organizers managed to adapt the course very well to the virtual environment."
		"It was very good. I would definitely do another one."
	Neutral	"It was interesting, I think it could be spread over more days because the hours felt a bit heavy."
		"Although I prefer the in-person format, I believe that adopting Slack + Meet + Google Colab adequately

		covered the course's needs, and I think the remote format is efficient for its execution."
		"It was normal, I'm already accustomed to the pace of distance learning courses. Yes."
	Negative experience	"[...] I believe that the learning in this course was hindered by the online method [...], as it was very difficult to follow the teacher's explanation and at the same time copy the code [...] Maybe I would take another online course, but only if I had a second screen available to connect to my notebook. However, I will definitely prefer in-person courses."

The responses contained in the feedback forms were translated from the original language (Portuguese).